

The Influence of Motivation, Organizational Commitment, and Leadership on Work Stress in Improving Nurse Performance at Royal Prima Hospital in Medan

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Abstract: The purpose of this study was to analyze the effect of motivation, organizational commitment, and leadership on nurses' work stress in improving the performance of nurses at the Royal Prima Hospital in Medan. This type of research is causality research. The population in this study were nurses at the Royal Prima Hospital, totaling 254 people in 2021. The sampling method used the Slovin formula with a sample of 72 people. Primary data collection using questionnaires and interviews. The results of this study found that motivation has a positive and significant effect on work stress, organizational commitment has a positive but not significant effect on work stress, leadership has a positive and significant effect on work stress, motivation has a positive and significant effect on nurse performance, organizational commitment has a positive but not significant effect. on the performance of nurses, leadership has a positive and significant effect on the performance of nurses, motivation has a positive and significant effect on the performance of nurses through work stress, organizational commitment has a positive but not significant effect on the performance of nurses through work stress, and leadership has a positive and significant effect on the performance of nurses through stress Work at the Royal Prima Hospital in Medan.

Keywords: Motivation, organizational commitment, leadership, work stress, nurse performance.

I. Introduction

Human Resources (HR) has an important role for all forms of organization, without exception for a hospital. The company will achieve performance if it has quality human resources. Hospitals or organizations need human resources who have high motivation so that these human resources can provide good performance and are enthusiastic to achieve high work performance.

Performance is a very important and interesting part because it proves to be very important in its benefits, because it will affect how much employees contribute to the company which includes quantity of output, quality of output, attendance and cooperative attitude. Hospitals want nurses to work seriously according to their abilities and main tasks to achieve maximum work results. If the nurse's performance is not optimal, it will have an impact on goals that will be difficult to achieve. Performance basically includes mental attitudes and behaviors that always have the view that the work carried out today must be of higher quality than the implementation of past work, for the future it will be of higher quality than today. Nurses will feel pride and satisfaction with the achievements achieved based on their performance. Good performance is a state desired by nurses. Nurses will get good work performance if their performance is in accordance with standards, both quality and quantity.

Nurses need to get special attention to find out what factors affect the performance of nurses. Nurse performance can be influenced by various things, such as: work stress, work discipline, leadership, performance, training, education, motivation, work environment, job training, recruitment, and organizational commitment.

The performance of nurses is expected to satisfy the needs of the patients, because it is the nurses who always communicate with the patients. Nurses must be able to serve patients patiently and deftly, provide good and correct

explanations, and be friendly to all patients. Through the performance of nurses who are very satisfying for patients, they can make patients come back if they need treatment at the Royal Prima Hospital in Medan. This is what makes the performance of nurses very important for a hospital.

Improving the performance of nurses will bring progress for Prima Medan Hospital to be able to survive in an unstable competitive business environment. Performance is a comparison of the work achieved by nurses with predetermined standards. Therefore, efforts to improve the performance of nurses are the most serious management challenges because success in achieving the vision and mission of the Royal Prima Hospital in Medan, one of which depends on the performance of the nurses owned by the hospital. The following is the performance data of the Royal Prima Hospital Medan nurses in the last five years from 2015-2020.

Table1. Royal Prima Hospital Nurse Performance Data 2015-2020

Year	Number Of Nurses	Criteria			
		Very Good	Good	Medium	Bad
2016	180	50	67	60	3
2017	206	100	49	55	2
2018	201	73	50	75	3
2019	220	64	80	68	8
2020	254	110	60	77	7

From Table 1 shows the results of the performance of nurses over the last few years there are still many nurses' performance at Prima Medan Hospital in the sufficient category and some in the poor category. If this continues, it will have a negative impact on nurses and the hospital itself. This condition can be concluded that the level of nurse performance from year to year (2015-2020) fluctuates and even tends to decrease. The tendency of decreasing nurse performance is certainly closely related to motivation, organizational commitment, leadership and work stress.

If you look at the results of the nurse's performance which have been described in Table 1, the average performance of nurses is still not optimal and their performance can still be improved. The better and more credible the nurse's performance is, the easier the vision and mission of the hospital will be realized and vice versa. If a hospital experiences a decrease in the performance of nurses, it will systematically interfere with other parts and can cause the quality of public health services to be not optimal.

Situationally, at the end of August 2021, Level 4 Community Activity Restrictions (PPKM) were implemented. The instruction was numbered 188.54/INST/2021 and was addressed to the Mayor of Medan Bobby Nasution. This is due to the increasing number of people exposed to Covid-19. So that the performance of nurses during this covid period is even more extra in providing health services for the community, especially during this pandemic, nurses are required to wear PPE clothes in carrying out their duties. This is a very difficult challenge for nurses in carrying out their duties. Not to mention the many negative views from the public regarding the service quality of the Royal Prima Hospital who prefer to refer patients to other hospitals rather than having to go to the Royal Prima Hospital Medan.

One of the causes of the decline in the performance of nurses is the motivation of the nurses which is still low. The low motivation is due to the leadership's low attention to the need for self-esteem and self-actualization of nurses which is characterized by problems in group adjustment for those who have completed education, and problems with promotion opportunities tend to be few due to the unavailability of the desired position. As a result, the motivation of the nurses to work hard to get a promotion or promotion is not there because they cannot get the position they want. There are also many nurses who always complain to other nurses, but never aspire to voice their voices to their superiors because they are afraid of being punished by the leadership.

One important factor that can affect performance is motivation. Lack of motivation for nurses can lead to decreased nurse performance. Motivation is an impulse from within a person as the reason that underlies the spirit of work in doing something or directing a person's behavior.

Of the 20 respondents, 50% felt they did not get primary needs, 60% felt they had not received security guarantees at work, 50% felt they did not have a good relationship with other nursing colleagues, and 70% felt they had never received special awards. This is a problem in the application of motivation. The results of research conducted by Ginatra (2016) that motivation affects employee performance. While the research results of Sarton Sinambela, et al (2020) show that motivation has no effect on employee performance.

Organizational commitment becomes an important thing in this day and age. When a hospital is very difficult to find nurses who have very good qualifications in doing their jobs, organizational commitment is one way to determine nurses who have qualifications, loyalty and good performance. In other words, organizational commitment is used as an important thing in determining nurses at the level of performance in a hospital.

Based on the results of the pre-survey for the Organizational Commitment variable, it can be concluded that nurses do not have high enough care. This means that the agency pays less attention to the organizational commitment of each nurse. High commitment will spur nurses to work as well as possible so that productivity can increase and hospital goals can be achieved. Therefore, a high commitment is very important for a hospital to achieve the expected goals.

The North Sumatra Provincial Government has made the Royal Prima Hospital the main referral location for handling Covid-19 patients in North Sumatra. Royal Prima has prepared 20 Intensive Care Unit (ICU) rooms for Covid patients. Royal Prima Hospital is intended for Covid-19 patients with severe conditions. Patients will be treated with complete facilities at the hospital. So that under these circumstances nurses are given facilities in the form of a special room for rest for nurses who specifically handle Covid-19 patients.

Prima Medan Hospital nurses have not all worked optimally, there are still some nurses who work as well as they can and make it work, so the work done is not optimal. In working, a nurse is not enough to always be present on time, but also needs to be seen seriousness and sincerity in work. The persistence of nurses can also indicate a person's motivation, such as the behavior of someone who still wants to work despite obstacles, problems, and obstacles. For example, if there is a problem with the weather or a nurse's health problem, does the nurse still come to work on time and really do her job as usual or choose other things, such as going home or not coming to work.

Research conducted by Adinata (2015) stated that there was an influence, while the results of research conducted by Purnama (2014) stated that there was no effect of organizational commitment on employee performance. Another important factor that can affect performance is leadership. Leadership is the most important role in organizations or hospitals because it affects the success of the organization or hospital in achieving goals. The success of an organization as a whole or part of an organization is very dependent on the quality of the leadership itself because a leader has the power to regulate his nurses to do something to achieve hospital goals. Thus the hospital needs a leader who is able to inspire, motivate, and move members of the organization effectively and efficiently to achieve the hospital's goals. The absence of leadership traits towards nurses can lead to decreased nurse performance. This can be seen from the results of a pre-survey conducted to 20 nurses. The leadership variable shows that the nurse leadership is still in the sufficient category at Prima Medan Hospital.

Based on the results of the pre-survey for the leadership variable, it can be concluded that they feel that they always work under a fairly high leadership line of command, because the leader always pays attention to work according to the direction of the nurse's self-confidence. However, in the form of assistance from superiors, it is still in the fairly low category. The difference in the results of research conducted by Asfari (2017) states that leadership has a positive and significant influence on employee performance, but in contrast to the results of research conducted by Sinambela, et al (2020) which states that there is no influence of leadership on employee performance. Job satisfaction is an assessment, feeling or attitude of a person or nurse towards his work and related to the work environment, relationships between co-workers, social relations at work, and so on.

Work stress is faced by almost all nurses in the work environment. The workload and work demands that must be completed in a short time will cause pressure on nurses. Work stress can also come from family stress. Lack of harmonious relations in the household or problems related to the family will certainly have an impact on employee performance at work. The necessity of mastering technology in the company is also a source of stress for nurses. During this covid-19 pandemic, nurses at every hospital, especially those who are referrals for covid patients, are one of them at the Royal Prima Hospital, where the stress level of nurses is very high due to very uncomfortable work demands.

Based on the results of the pre-survey for the work stress variable, it can be concluded that nurses still have a high level of work stress. One of the things that must be the main concern of a hospital is the work stress of the nurses. Because when nurses at work feel high stress, they will not be able to develop all their potential, then automatically nurses cannot focus and concentrate fully on their work or in carrying out the assigned tasks. The difference in the results of research conducted by Sanjaya (2012) shows that work stress has a negative effect on employee performance, but on the contrary the results of research conducted by Sutrisno (2014) show that work stress has no effect on employee performance.

Based on the description above, to determine the effect of motivation, organizational commitment and leadership on nurse performance mediated by work stress variables, this research will be carried out. The conceptual framework of this research is as follows:

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

The hypotheses used in the research are:

- Hypothesis 1 : Motivation has a positive and significant effect on work stress at Royal Prima Hospital Medan.
- Hypothesis 2 : Organizational Commitment has a positive and significant effect on Work Stress at Royal Prima Hospital Medan.
- Hypothesis 3 : Leadership has a positive and significant effect on work stress at Royal Prima Hospital Medan.
- Hypothesis 4 : Motivation has a positive and significant effect on the performance of nurses at the Royal Prima Hospital in Medan.
- Hypothesis 5 : Organizational commitment has a positive and significant effect on the performance of nurses at the Royal Prima Hospital in Medan.
- Hypothesis 6 : Leadership has a positive and significant effect on the performance of nurses at the Royal Prima Hospital in Medan.
- Hypothesis 7 : Motivation has a positive and significant effect on the performance of nurses through work stress at the Royal Prima Hospital in Medan.
- Hypothesis 8 : Organizational commitment has a positive and significant effect on the performance of nurses through work stress at the Royal Prima Hospital in Medan.
- Hypothesis 9 : Leadership has a positive and significant effect on the performance of nurses through work stress at the Royal Prima Hospital in Medan.

II. Methodology

This research is causality research. Causality research is a study conducted to investigate cause-and-effect relationships by observing the effects that occur and the possible causal factors that cause these effects. In causality research, there are independent variables (cause) namely the variables that influence, and the dependent variable (effects) namely the variables that are influenced (Sinulingga: 2014). This study aims to examine and analyze the influence of motivation, organizational commitment, and leadership on work stress in improving the performance of nurses at the Royal Prima Hospital in Medan.

This research was conducted at the Royal Prima Hospital in Medan which is located on Jalan Ayahanda No. 68A, Sei Putih Tengah, Kec. Medan Petisah, Medan City, North Sumatra 20118. This research is planned from September to December 2021. The population in this study were nurses at the Royal Prima Hospital, totaling 254 people in 2021.

The sample is part of the total population (Sugiyono: 2012). This research uses the Slovin formula because in sampling, the number must be representative so that the research results can be generalized and the calculations do not require a table of the number of samples, but can be done with simple formulas and calculations. The Slovin formula for determining the sample is as follows:

$$n = \frac{254}{1 + 254(0,1)^2} = 71,75 = 72$$

The sample of 72 people will be divided into three parts according to the nurse division at the Royal Prima Hospital in Medan, so that the answers from the respondents spread to all existing nurses.

The data collection techniques that researchers use are questionnaires, interviews and documentation studies. The source of this research comes from the source directly and requires further processing of the data obtained. Based on the source, the data is divided into two, namely primary data and secondary data. According to Sujarweni (2014) what is meant by primary data is "data obtained from respondents through questionnaires, focus groups and panels or also data from researchers' interviews with resource persons. Data sources that directly provide data to data collectors.

This research uses data analysis with Partial Least Square (PLS) approach. Where PLS is an equation model of Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) based on variables or components. PLS is an alternative approach that shifts from a covariance-based SEM approach to a variant-based approach (Ghozali and Latan, 2015). This research was conducted using Smart PLS V.3.0 software which was run on computer media.

III. Results

Model Analysis Results

Measurement model is a model with calculation results based on calculations using the PLS program. The purpose of the measurement model is to describe which indicator has a dominant influence as a direct measure of the latent variable.

Evaluation of the measurement model (outer model) is an evaluation of the correlation between the construct and its indicators which is carried out by testing the validity and reliability of the indicators forming the latent variable by means of Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA). The construct validity test shows how well the results obtained from the use of a measurement are in accordance with the theories used to define a construct. A strong correlation between the construct and its statement items and a weak relationship with other variables is one way to test construct validity. Construct validity consists of convergent validity and discriminant validity. In addition to construct validity tests, construct reliability tests were also carried out as measured by composite reliability of the indicator block measuring constructs, because composite reliability measures the real value of construct reliability. The outer model test begins by estimating or estimating parameters, namely by calculating the PLS algorithm with the following results.

Figure 2. PLS Algorithm (Calculation Output Display)

From the output of the analysis, the measurement model (outermodel) can be evaluated, namely by testing convergent validity, discriminant validity and reliability.

Convergent Validity Test Results

Convergent validity test is done by looking at the value of the loading factor on each construct. A loading factor value above 0.7 is declared as an ideal or valid measure as an indicator in measuring the construct, values from 0.5 to 0.6 are still acceptable, while values below 0.5 must be excluded from the model. The loading factor value of each indicator can be obtained by calculating the data using the PLS algorithm method.

Table2. Loading Factor Value Before Reduction

Variable	Indicator	LoadingFactor	Description
Motivation (X ₁)	MT1	0,770	Valid
	MT2	0,775	Valid
	MT3	0,745	Valid
	MT4	0,782	Valid
	MT5	0,680	Valid
	MT6	0,726	Valid
	MT7	0,764	Valid
	MT8	0,756	Valid
	MT9	0,806	Valid
	MT10	0,784	Valid
	MT11	0,733	Valid
Organizational Commitment(X ₂)	KO1	0,819	Valid
	KO2	0,734	Valid
	KO3	0,744	Valid
	KO4	0,739	Valid
	KO5	0,758	Valid
	KO6	0,639	Valid
	KO7	0,754	Valid
	KO8	0,774	Valid
	KO9	0,814	Valid
	KO10	0,705	Valid
	KO11	0,783	Valid
	KO12	0,750	Valid
	KO13	0,785	Valid
	KO14	0,701	Valid
	KO15	0,528	Valid
Leadership(X ₃)	KN1	0,652	Valid
	KN2	0,781	Valid
	KN3	0,861	Valid
	KN4	0,901	Valid
	KN5	0,907	Valid
	KN6	0,891	Valid
	KN7	0,791	Valid
	KN8	0,867	Valid

Variable	Indicator	LoadingFactor	Description
Nurse Performance(Y)	KP1	0,790	Valid
	KP2	0,800	Valid
	KP3	0,823	Valid
	KP4	0,776	Valid
	KP5	0,799	Valid
	KP6	0,812	Valid
	KP7	0,801	Valid
	KP8	0,767	Valid
	KP9	0,844	Valid
	KP10	0,845	Valid
	KP11	0,760	Valid
	KP12	0,702	Valid
	KP13	0,715	Valid
Work Stress(Z)	SK1	0,846	Valid
	SK2	0,842	Valid
	SK3	0,864	Valid
	SK4	0,867	Valid
	SK5	0,856	Valid
	SK6	0,771	Valid

Based on Table 2, all indicators are stated to represent Motivation Variables (X1), Organizational Commitment (X2), Leadership (X3), Work Stress (Z), and Nurse Performance (Y), the conclusion that all indicators have met the reliability criteria for each indicator. -each construct. Thus, the outer model analysis was continued by looking at the internal consistency reliability of each construct.

Internal consistency reliability assessment was carried out on each construct. The composite reliability value of each construct is expected to be at least 0.7. However, in exploratory research, the composite reliability value of 0.6 is acceptable. The results of the SmartPLS algorithm on the composite reliability of each construct are presented in Table 2.

Table 3. CompositeReliability

Variable	CompositeReliability
Motivation	0,936
Organizational Commitment	0,947
Leadership	0,936
Nurse Performance	0,955
Work Stress	0,948

Table 3 shows that the category is quite good, each construct has met the outer model reliability assessment criteria with a composite reliability value > 0.7. Thus the analysis of the outer model is continued to the outer model validity stage. The validity of the outer model is carried out using convergent validity and discriminant validity. Convergent validity assessment is carried out by looking at the average variance extracted (AVE) value in each construct. Hair et al. (2011) stated that the AVE value for each good construct was at least 0.5. The results of the Smart PLS Algorithm on the AVE value are summarized in Table 4.

Table 4. AverageVarianceExtraced

Variabel	AverageVarianceExtraced
Motivation	0,573
Organizational Commitment	0,546
Leadership	0,698
Nurse Performance	0,621
Work Stress	0,708

Table 4 shows that the AVE value of each dimensional construct in the final model has reached a value of > 0.5. Thus, the proposed structural equation model has met the convergent validity criteria. Discriminant validity assessment is carried out using two methods, by using a comparison between the correlation of each construct to the square root of its AVE based on the Fornell-Lacker criteria, or by comparing the loading factor with the cross loading of each indicator (Hair et al., 2014). The value of R2 is used to measure the level of variation of changes in the independent variable to the dependent variable. The R2 value of this study can be seen in the following table:

Tabel 5. RSquare

	RSquare	RSquareAdjusted
Nurse Performance	0,889	0,882
Work Stress	0,695	0,681

Based on Table 5 the R Square value for the Work Stress variable is 69.5% which means that it is included in the Strong category. while the remaining 30.5% is explained by other variables outside the research model. And the R Square value for the Nurse Performance variable is 88.9%, which means that it is included in the Very Strong category, while the remaining 12.1% is explained by other variables outside the research model.

Inner Model Analysis

Inner model analysis is done by estimating the path coefficient of the relationship between constructs. Estimation is done by SmartPLS algorithm. The value of the path coefficient on the relationship between variables becomes a reference in making estimates. A positive value indicates a positive influence and a negative value indicates a negative effect. The greater the value of the path coefficient, the greater the influence between these variables. However, the path coefficient in SmartPLS cannot be a reference for the exact value of the relationship between variables.

The analysis of the inner model on the structural model with mediating variables is carried out by looking at the direct, indirect, and total effects between variables. The direct effect is the magnitude of the effect that occurs directly from the independent variable on the dependent variable. Indirect influence is the magnitude of the influence that occurs indirectly, but through the mediation of the mediator variable. The total effect is the sum of the direct and indirect effects of each independent variable on the dependent variable.

Direct Effect

The results of the SmartPLS algorithm in assessing the Path Coefficient directly are given in Table 6.

Table 6. Path Coefficient

Sample (O)	Mean (M)	Standar Deviasi (STDEV)	TStatistic (O/STDEV)	P Values	
Leadership-> Nurse Performance	0,159	0,160	0,059	2,693	0,007
Leadership-> Work Stress	-0,396	0,403	0,083	4,746	0,000
Organizational Commitment-> Nurse Performance	0,062	0,057	0,068	0,916	0,360
Organizational Commitment-> Work Stress	-0,146	0,145	0,109	1,346	0,179
Motivation ->Nurse Performance	0,234	0,230	0,070	3,326	0,001
Motivation ->Work Stress	-0,383	0,377	0,135	2,845	0,005

The following is a discussion of each hypothesis test based on the test results which are summarized in Table 6:

The Effect of Motivation on Work Stress, Based on Table 6 explains that the effect of motivation on work stress ($p = 0.005 < 0.05$) then H_0 is rejected, meaning that there is a positive and significant effect between motivation and work stress at a significant level of 5%.

The Effect of Organizational Commitment on Work Stress, Based on Table 6 explains that the effect of Organizational Commitment on Work Stress ($p = 0.179 > 0.05$) then H_0 is accepted, meaning that there is no significant effect between Organizational Commitment and Work Stress at a significant level of 5%.

The Effect of Leadership on Work Stress, Based on Table 6 explains that the influence of Leadership on Work Stress ($p = 0.000 < 0.05$) then H_0 is rejected, meaning that there is a positive and significant influence between Leadership and Nurse Performance at a significant level of 5%.

The Effect of Motivation on Nurse Performance, Based on Table 6 explains that the influence of Motivation on Nurse Performance ($p = 0.001 < 0.05$) then H_0 is rejected H_a is accepted, meaning that there is a positive and significant effect between Motivation and Nurse Performance at a significant level of 5%.

The Effect of Organizational Commitment on Nurse Performance, Based on Table 6 explains that the effect of Organizational Commitment on Nurse Performance ($p = 0.360 > 0.05$) then H_0 is accepted, meaning that there is no significant effect between Organizational Commitment and Nurse Performance at a significant level of 5%.

The Effect of Leadership on Nurse Performance, Based on Table 6 explains that the influence of Leadership on Nurse Performance ($p = 0.007 < 0.05$) then H_0 is rejected, meaning that there is a positive and significant influence between Leadership and Nurse Performance at a significant level of 5%.

Indirect Effect

Indirect influence is the amount of influence through the mediating variable. The magnitude of the indirect effect is the product of the direct effect of the independent variable on the mediating variable and the direct effect of the mediating variable on the dependent variable. The magnitude of the indirect effect of the independent variable on the variable can be calculated and summarized in Table 7.

Table 7. Indirecteffect

Sample (O)	(M)	(STDEV)	TStatistic	P Values	
Organizational Commitment ->Work Stress -> Nurse Performance	0,098	0,094	0,070	1,396	0,163
Motivation ->Work Stress - >Nurse Performance	0,257	0,255	0,100	2,559	0,011
Leadership->Work Stress ->Nurse Performance	0,266	0,269	0,058	4,542	0,000

Based on Table 7 then the results of research to answer the hypotheses contained in the previous chapter are as follows:

The Effect of Motivation on Nurse Performance Through Work Stress, Table 7 shows that empirical evidence that motivation on performance through work stress, there is an indirect effect of motivation on nurses' performance through work stress with P Values $0.011 < 0.05$. The bootstrap results indicate that this indirect effect is significant so that H0 is rejected.

The Effect of Organizational Commitment on Nurse Performance Through Work Stress, Table 7 shows that empirical evidence that Organizational Commitment to Performance through Work Stress, there is no indirect effect of Organizational Commitment to Nurse Performance through Work Stress with P Values $0.163 > 0.05$. The results of the bootstrap indicate that this indirect effect is not significant so that H0 is accepted.

The Effect of Leadership on Nurse Performance Through Work Stress, Table 7 shows that empirical evidence that Leadership on Performance through Work Stress, there is an indirect effect of Leadership on Nurse Performance through Work Stress with P Values $0.000 < 0.05$. The bootstrap results indicate that this indirect effect is significant so that H0 is rejected.

The Effect of Motivation on Work Stress at Royal Prima Hospital Medan

Based on the results of the direct effect test, it is known that motivation has a negative and significant effect on work stress. It can be concluded that the higher the motivation possessed by the nurse, the more capable the nurse is to cope with the work stress she feels. This is because the level of work stress of nurses at the Royal Prima Hospital Medan does not implement the obtained motivation into work activities. Where motivation is a psychological process that reflects the interaction between attitudes, needs, perceptions and decisions that occur within a person. In carrying out daily tasks, motivation is defined as the whole process of giving encouragement or stimulation to nurses so that they are willing to work together willingly and without being forced.

Based on the distribution of answers, it is known that the average answer to questions from motivation is 4.00, which according to several nurses at the Royal Prima Hospital Medan has given motivation to nurses in carrying out work in the form of meetings or verbally. Generally, nurses at Prima Medan Hospital are mostly in the age range of 25-35 years, this is because that age is very much needed in a nursing position.

The results of this study are in line with what was said by Dewi et al, (2013) that motivation has a positive effect on work stress. According to Hasibuan (2012), work stress can trigger a decrease in performance. The same thing was stated by Robbins & Judge (2008) who said that when there is too much work stress experienced by employees due to excessive work demands or cannot be achieved, it will have an impact on decreasing employee performance.

The Effect of Organizational Commitment on Work Stress at Royal Prima Hospital Medan

Based on the results of the direct effect test, it is known that organizational commitment has a negative and insignificant effect on work stress. If the organizational commitment increases, the work stress felt by nurses will increase.

Based on the available demographic data, it shows that the younger respondents have a lower commitment to the organization than the older respondents. This can be said in accordance with research conducted by Baron in Khanifar, et al. (2012) which states that organizational commitment can be formed from the age factor. In addition, the results of Sakina's (2009) research reveal that individuals who have early adulthood tend to have low commitment.

Based on the distribution of answers, it is known that based on the average it is known that respondents still dominantly agree with all statements with the lowest mean value of 3.96, where according to some nurses themselves, their organizational commitment is not too committed, this is because of the basic necessities of life by the nurses themselves. like it or not, they must have a commitment to the Royal Prima Hospital in Medan.

From the many journals that have found a positive relationship between organizational commitment and work stress, it turns out that this is in line with the results of research conducted. Where the more Agree with organizational commitment, the more Agree The work stress felt by nurses because they are in a depressed state if they have emotional ties with the organization including co-workers and superiors, the nurse's commitment to the organization remains Agree even in a state of stress, that's why the results show that there is a relationship positive correlation between organizational commitment to nurses' work stress.

The results of this study are not in line with what was said by Dewi et al, (2013) that work stress has a negative effect on employee performance. According to Hasibuan (2012), work stress can trigger a decrease in performance. This is in line with Robbins & Judge (2008) which states that when there is too much work stress experienced by employees due to excessive or unattainable work demands, it will have an impact on decreasing employee performance

The Effect of Leadership on Work Stress at Royal Prima Hospital Medan

Based on the results of the direct influence test, it is known that leadership has a negative and significant effect on work stress. This means that good leadership can cause nurses to be more productive and creative when carrying out work so that it has an impact on achieving the career that nurses aspire to which makes employees feel less stressed about their work. Company leaders should be able to have good interactions with nurses and behave well and fairly to nurses so that nurses feel comfortable while working and can reduce their stress levels.

Leadership is a technique carried out by leaders so that the people they lead do what they are assigned responsibly so that the goals of the organization are achieved. The results of this study are supported by Sari Rindah (2016), Fadhila (2015) and Eldy (2014) who state that leadership has a negative relationship to work stress.

The Effect of Motivation on the Performance of Nurses at Royal Prima Hospital Medan

Based on the results of the direct effect test, it is known that motivation has a positive and significant effect on Nurse Performance. Based on the results of the study showed that the motivation given by the hospital was good so that the nurses were motivated to work even better. Hospitals must maintain and increase motivation to nurses so that nurses are more comfortable and understand and are more motivated to work. This result is supported by I Putu Gandi Ginatra (2016) that motivation has an effect on employee performance. Meanwhile, the results of the research by Sarton Sinambela, et al (2020) show that motivation has no effect on employee performance.

This result is also supported by the opinion of Hasibuan (2013), motivation is the provision of a driving force that creates one's work enthusiasm so that they want to work together, work effectively, and be integrated with all their efforts to achieve satisfaction. The importance of providing motivation because motivation is the thing that causes, distributes and supports human behavior, so that they are willing to work hard and enthusiastically to achieve optimal results. Motivation is increasingly important because managers share work with their subordinates to be done well and integrated into the desired goals. In other words, giving motivation to nurses is very necessary in a hospital to be able to improve the performance of a nurse in order to achieve hospital goals.

The effect of organizational commitment on the performance of nurses at the Royal Prima Hospital Medan

Based on the results of the direct effect test, it is known that organizational commitment has a positive and insignificant effect on Nurse Performance. Nurses feel uncomfortable when working, because all nurses at work are required to run and obey the applicable rules, not to mention during this covid 19 pandemic, using personal protective equipment

according to the work area, all nurse needs are still not being met by hospitals such as profit sharing, Health benefits include BPJS Health and Health Insurance for all nurses and their families.

Commitment should really encourage nurses to work better, nurses and their families feel very appreciated by the hospital. Because the more agree the organizational commitment of nurses will improve the performance of nurses so as to increase the loyalty of nurses to hospitals, and vice versa, the lower the organizational commitment of nurses causes a decrease in nurse performance, this has a very bad impact on the progress of hospitals, because organizational commitment is a strong foundation to determine the success of a hospital. This is in accordance with the opinion of Luthans in Priansa (2016), loyal employees to the hospital are the nurses concerned, of course they will give the best for the company, one of which is by showing the best performance as an employee. Good performance is a reflection of the loyalty and commitment of nurses to do the best for the hospital.

The results of this study are in line with research conducted by Adinata (2015) partially organizational commitment has no significant effect on employee performance. Organizational commitment is still low, hospitals must foster a sense of involvement and loyalty of employees to the organization.

The influence of leadership on the performance of nurses at the Royal Prima Hospital Medan

Based on the direct influence test, it is known that leadership has a positive and significant effect on Nurse Performance through work stress. Based on the results of the research conducted, it shows that the leadership at the Royal Prima Hospital Medan should be even better so that the performance of the nurses can be maximized so that the goals of the Royal Prima Hospital Medan can be achieved. These results are supported by research conducted by Sinambela, et al (2020), Mamahit (2016), Bahriansyah, DKK (2018), and Rahmat Asfari (2017) that leadership is one of the factors that can support improving performance. The increasing leadership possessed by the leader will make a major contribution to improving the performance of nurses at the Royal Prima Hospital in Medan. Therefore, nurse leaders should be able to improve better leadership and create a good atmosphere to improve the performance of nurses at the Royal Prima Hospital in Medan.

Leadership has a significant influence in a hospital so that it is expected to be able to protect and be fair to every nurse because the performance of a hospital affects how a leader or manager establishes a good relationship with his nurses.

The effect of motivation on nurse performance through work stress at Royal Prima Hospital Medan

Based on the indirect effect test, it is known that motivation has a positive and significant effect on Nurse Performance through work stress. In this study, work stress was measured by three indicators, namely physical symptoms, psychological symptoms and behavioral symptoms. Based on the descriptive analysis of the three indicators, employee work stress is in the medium category, namely the average number is below 4.00. The fatigue experienced by nurses makes nurses consume drugs more often, work permits more often and work results begin to decline. So that employee behavior begins to show a change in attitude at work. Such as work results that are starting to be inconsistent so that work productivity results are disrupted. It is not impossible even though it is dominated by nurses who are still young, the workload that agrees makes nurses feel enthusiastic about work can also decrease. At a young age with emotions that are sometimes unstable, nurses will more easily experience work stress. Handoko (2011) said that work stress will have an impact on employees' emotions, thinking patterns, and enthusiasm at work. Meanwhile, Veithzal & Sagala (2004) say that too much work stress can threaten a person in dealing with their environment.

These results are supported by research conducted by Veronica Abu Brobbey and Masud Ibrahim (2015), Sitompul (2018), Bahriansyah, DKK (2018), and Rahmat Asfari (2017). Where the results, motivation partially positive and significant effect on employee performance.

Based on the distribution of answers, it is known that based on the average it is known that respondents still dominantly agree with all statements, but some respondents have several problems such as the statement "I feel responsible in carrying out nursing care, especially in meeting the patient's personal hygiene needs" with the lowest mean value, namely 3.74, which according to several nurses at the Royal Prima Hospital Medan never motivated nurses to learn to carry out nursing care to patients as a form of remedial action, this was approved by nurses because usually the Royal Prima Hospital Medan did not respond to complaints from customers. This is certainly an important task of the Royal Prima Hospital Medan in fixing the motivation of nurses.

The Effect of Organizational Commitment on the performance of nurses through work stress at Royal Prima Hospital Medan

Based on the indirect effect test, it is known that organizational commitment has a positive but not significant effect on Nurse Performance through work stress. In this study, work stress was measured by three indicators, namely physical symptoms, psychological symptoms and behavioral symptoms. Based on the descriptive analysis of the three indicators, employee work stress is in the medium category, namely the average number is below 4.00. The fatigue experienced by nurses makes nurses consume drugs more often, work permits more often and work results begin to decline. So that employee behavior begins to show a change in attitude at work. Such as work results that are starting to be inconsistent so that work productivity results are disrupted. It is not impossible even though it is dominated by nurses who are still young, the workload that agrees makes nurses feel enthusiastic about work can also decrease. At a young age with emotions that are sometimes unstable, nurses will more easily experience work stress. Handoko (2011) said that work stress will have an impact on employees' emotions, thinking patterns, and enthusiasm at work. Meanwhile, Veithzal & Sagala (2004) say that too much work stress can threaten a person in dealing with their environment.

The results of this study are in line with research conducted by Rajaguguk (2016) partially organizational commitment has no significant effect on employee performance. Organizational commitment is still low, hospitals must foster a sense of involvement and loyalty of employees to the organization.

Based on the distribution of answers, it is known that based on the average it is known that respondents still dominantly agree with all statements, but some respondents have several problems such as the statement "Have confidence in the goals and values of Royal Prima Hospital" with the lowest mean value of 3.75, where according to some nurses at the Royal Prima Hospital Medan did not apologize to the patient as a form of remedial action, this was agreed by the respondents because usually the Royal Prima Medan Hospital did not respond to complaints from customers. This is certainly an important task of the Royal Prima Hospital Medan in fixing the motivation of nurses.

The influence of leadership on nurse performance through work stress at Royal Prima Hospital Medan

Based on the indirect effect test, it is known that leadership has a positive and significant effect on Nurse Performance through work stress. In this study, work stress was measured by three indicators, namely physical symptoms, psychological symptoms and behavioral symptoms. Based on the descriptive analysis of the three indicators, employee work stress is in the medium category, namely the average number is below 4.00. The fatigue experienced by nurses makes nurses consume drugs more often, work permits more often and work results begin to decline. So that employee behavior begins to show a change in attitude at work. Such as work results that are starting to be inconsistent so that work productivity results are disrupted. It is not impossible even though it is dominated by nurses who are still young, the workload that agrees makes nurses feel enthusiastic about work can also decrease. At a young age with sometimes unstable emotions will make nurses more easily experience work stress. Handoko (2011) said that work stress will have an impact on employees' emotions, thinking patterns, and enthusiasm at work. Meanwhile, Veithzal & Sagala (2004) say that too much work stress can threaten a person in dealing with their environment.

These results are supported by research conducted by Mamahit (2016), Bahriansyah, DKK (2018), and Rahmat Asfari (2017) that leadership is one of the factors that can support improving performance.

IV. Conclusion

Based on the analysis and discussion of the influence of motivation, organizational commitment, and leadership on nurse work stress in improving nurse performance at the Royal Prima Hospital in Medan, several conclusions can be drawn, namely, motivation has a negative and significant effect on work stress at the Royal Prima Hospital, Medan. Organizational commitment has a negative but not significant effect on work stress. Leadership has a negative and significant effect on work stress at Royal Prima Hospital Medan. Motivation has a positive and significant effect on the performance of nurses at the Royal Prima Hospital in Medan. Organizational commitment has a positive but not significant effect on the performance of nurses at the Royal Prima Hospital in Medan. Leadership has a positive and significant effect on the performance of nurses at the Royal Prima Hospital in Medan. Motivation has a positive and significant effect on the performance of nurses through work stress at the Royal Prima Hospital in Medan. Organizational commitment has a positive but not significant effect on the performance of nurses through work stress at Royal Prima Hospital, Medan. Leadership has a positive and significant effect on the performance of nurses through work stress at the Royal Prima Hospital in Medan.

Based on the results of the study, as for things that researchers can suggest that can be input and attention, it is hoped that Royal Prima Hospital can maintain and improve motivation and leadership because it has a dominant influence in influencing the performance of nurses. In addition, what needs special attention for the Royal Prima Hospital Medan so that in the future it can be even better is the organizational commitment variable. Due to the limitations of the researcher, it is hoped that further researchers will further refine this research by using factors other than those studied by the researcher, further researchers can add other variables such as job satisfaction, work discipline or can research other similar service provider companies because there are so many in the future. recently.

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